

RE: "Why is the Stupid Plague spreading everywhere?"

MESS 0006

The POS Wave continues... because ((Agenda))

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
September 2022

ABSTRACT

A look at some massive swaths of treasonous, vindictive, race-baiting or politics-pushing actors (some are literally actors) who create problems and foment hatred between different groups to benefit anti-Western, anti-American, anti-Ally agendas, ultimately supporting Marxism, fascism, anarchism, and thereby murdering classical liberalism. In this paper the author breaks down a few categories where we see growth in the POS¹ (looter-moochers, traitors, society destroyers, etc.) sectors and *where possible*, it can be tied to "the Message." That's just another way to define the Agenda of pushing a New Cold War, the [cultural] Civil War, and World War 3.0 in order to weaken Western societies (the Allies: in order to win a 100+ year old war against bad German philosophy... and ultimately World War III.)

Keywords: BLM - antifa - Soros - WEF - Klaus Schwab - China CCP - Agenda 2030 - LOCKSTEP

¹ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

Dear Readers,

The Agenda, the Agendizers, and the Agendites

The Agenda is *anything* that is meant to (in support of the Rockefeller-Kissinger² initiative) undermine: families, Christianity (from a community perspective), patriotism, conservatism, government by the People, racial harmony and progress, liberality (defined as human rights and freedoms, not social perversions), and (more recently) *food supplies, logistics/supply chain, survival/resiliency*, and of course strategic³ and common energy reserves⁴ and resources.

The Agendites are divided into two large categories: paid actors/shills, we'll call these the POS Supremes *the ones who take money to destroy our society), and the ones conforming to the mass formation psychosis⁵ - the Zeitgeist⁶ of crazytown - and whatever Stand Alone Complex⁷ is pushed by Tik-tok and Twitter. We'll call these the POS Simpremes, or simply simps⁸ for short.

POS Supremes	The Deep State/FBI	Mainstream Media	DINOs & RINOs ⁹	The Axis & Sons
POS Simpremes	SJWs (various)	Trashademia	Stupid Kids	Race-hustlers

There is a category of criminal terrorists that lubricates this machine of clueterf--k, headed by POS Supremes like the Clintons, Bidens, or Bushes of the world, but not only. With connections to cartels and mafia types, or terrorist POS: this entire gang of the middlemen of *shit*, we will simply call "the Shits" because no one seems to care about how terrible they are, even though they should. You should give a shit, because people in this category, for example NGO heads like Klaus Schwab¹⁰, are trying to create world genocide, and they absolutely "care" about you (like: your future, your property, your kids...) If you don't look or sound a certain way, or agree with their Values (policies and topics matter little), they are more than willing to harm you, your families, your livelihoods, etc. They have historically used force to do so, but nowadays with the Web 2.0 debacle of Big Data and global spying being what it is, they can pretty much write algorithms and AI to flick the switches to push your buttons.

POS Supremes

- ❖ The Deep State is comprised of out-of-control, self-interested, unelected, self-governing alphabet agencies¹¹, and their fat-cat friends, lawyers, contractors and lobbyists. The FBI is top supreme POS

²

https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about pp.39-41

³

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/politics/2022/07/12/misplaced-outrage-over-hunter-biden-us-oil-reserves-bought-by-china/>

⁴ <https://www.nbcnews.com/data-graphics/biden-us-oil-reserves-drop-40-percent-rcna22855>

⁵ <https://www.swfinstitute.org/news/90470/what-is-mass-formation-psychosis>

⁶ [YouTube](#) Zeitgeist: The Movie

⁷ <https://robertsspaceindustries.com/orgs/COMPLEX>

⁸ "Simpin' ain't easy."

⁹ "Democrats in name only" & "Republicans in name only."

¹⁰ <https://www.henrymakow.com/2020/12/reset-modelled-on-Communist-china.html>

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alphabet_agencies

right now, as they are willing to send 25 useless trash agents at a time to go after pro-lifers¹², or to spend endless money and resources saving their own asses from prison so they can play politics with President Orange-Man-Bad on an issue clearly related to State and DOJ related Clintonization. Pathetic.

- ❖ The Mainstream Media has always been, since the inception of CNN, comprised of talking dogs that will bark at anything they are paid to; or to say any tripe they are told to. It is not the Cronkite era, folks, and “The Network” warned you. But now they appear to be paid to sit on anything negative about China, Soros (POS Supreme #1), RINO activity, COVID failures, globalist hackster fraudulism, etc. They spin everything, and in the process sell your countries down the river. Selfish.
- ❖ DINO & RINO: two things that should be extinct but sadly roam the Earth. The Democrat Party is already systemic racism itself, so with Democrats pretending to be liberal, or “for the workers”, it’s only that much more swampy. RINOs are so spineless and selling out their own base, it’s a wonder that liberal and conservative voters don’t just put aside small differences to get together and create an American Party. The two-party system is a blight on humanity. These people no longer have souls... they literally serve mammon.
- ❖ The Axis (China-Russia, aka *Chussia*, Iran, N. Korea, etc.) is a progenitor of tyranny and various Asiatic and/or Germanic traditions of Machiavellian dictatorships. Which, let’s be honest, are central to the Human Flesh Industry! Moreover, they are full of corruption and a willingness to subvert entire cultures (eg. Tibet). Their “Sons” are agents that work for them, like Congresswoman D. Feinstein¹³ (and others), Dr. Fauci, some entire NGOs (like the WHO), and even entire governments, like the UN, and maybe the EU! These Supremes are constantly pushing to enact/enable the Deep + Police State, and they are headed up by globalist power elites that are, like it or not, either in secret societies, or are Malthusian, or both.

POS Simpemes - the Simps

No one respects lapdogs and jack-booted thugs for a reason. They are despicable, weak-minded simpletons who are willing to do whatever they are told - just like in “The Animal Farm,” as Orwell predicted. He and Huxley - among others - predicted this era we are in, but even they couldn’t imagine the power that Big Data would give the FAANG in order to enact this Devil. China, for example, has entire classes of minders, whose sole job is to follow, censor, and report on their neighbors to local CCP branches, for “message” reasons. When the 3 scientists were ordered to leak the exosome to the wet market, they were made to disappear, and this is not a surprise in any society built in this way. Closer to home, the author reported the words of esteemed Nobel Winner Luc Montagnier¹⁴, discoverer of HIV¹⁵, about the faux-vaccine¹⁶ for COVID. He was whistleblowing about prions, and we now see massive upsurges in sudden and instant death among athletes, and increased infections¹⁷ in those that took the fauxines. When the author shared this, Simp corporations like Discord censored him, deleting his account without warning or identifying the specific cause - for fear of lawsuits. Control from the New World Order is *ordained*.

¹² <https://www.theblaze.com/shows/the-glenn-beck-program/fbi-raids-mark-houck-home>

¹³ <https://nypost.com/2018/08/08/dianne-feinstein-was-an-easy-mark-for-chinas-spy/> (sure, it was an accident)

¹⁴ <https://www.soulask.com/luc-montagnier-they-are-not-vaccines-they-are-poisons-speech-to-the-luxembourg-parliament/>

¹⁵ <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/medicine/2008/montagnier/facts/>

¹⁶ <https://www.citizensjournal.us/the-cdc-suddenly-changes-the-definition-of-vaccine-and-vaccination-2/>

¹⁷ <https://www.armstrongeconomics.com/international-news/disease/young-athletes-dying-after-covid-19-vaccine/>

- ❖ Social Justice Warriors, from antifa terrorists to BLM® actors and apologists for a notorious anti-family¹⁸, anti-black male communist organization¹⁹ headed by embezzlers²⁰, to more locally: perverted teachers pushing pedophilia and race-hucksterism in classrooms, as well as, of course, fake US History²¹... well they all suck. Not a single one is capable of deep thought, open debate, and they are socially reprehensible people. To the degree that even the Crips & Bloods gangs kicked them out of their neighborhoods²². These groups are willing to burn down homes, destroy downtowns, loot stores, vandalize²³ and terrorize minorities for “protection” money²⁴, and, of course, have a plethora of rapist criminals that will attack innocent children. Especially innocent white male children like N. Sandmann²⁵ and K. Rittenhouse²⁶. No wonder they are typically unemployed/unemployable! Anti-social is too nice a term for them. #CancerCulture
- ❖ And where do these simps get their ideas? From Trashademia. Academia which is composed almost entirely of “Studies” instead of STEMM, or forces STEMM to do racist and sexist quotas to conform to politically correct and *unequal* and *illegal* policies. Who almost Universally agree they should restrict the views and words of those they disagree with (so much for liberalism)... make the worst, and now most perverted, perverse-pushing, gender mutilating, child-destroying group of hucksters. They are simps because they suck from the “blue check” corporate teet, which gets its cues from the Agenda-controlled power elite establishment: the banks and NGOs (like Blackrock & World Economic Forum). But they also encourage simperism and bowing the knee to fascism among society’s most vulnerable: the kids. That is, at least the ones that manage to get born now that the far Left admits enjoying killing babies²⁷, especially white male ones²⁸.
- ❖ Stupid Kids are the result. These kids are not merely ignorant from all the Common Crap they were taught - or not taught? They not only are increasingly illiterate²⁹ and think math is racist³⁰ (thereby proving themselves to be racist). They actually hate words, people, entire groups of races³¹ and ethnicities, and then run around literally screaming obscenities instead of learning dialectic and dialogue. They are incredibly dull in personality, despite having an excess of fake ones, learned ostensibly from social media (vapid, narcissism replete with Duning-Krugerism), and as such are bad at social adjustment. This is reflected in the hilarious issues they have with memeing³², understanding context, and writing terrible stand up comedy³³. More interestingly, they are incapable of grasping why a lack of body shaming replaced with total acceptance (instead of tolerance) is actually unhealthy. In short: Stupid Kids don’t know anything about boundary conditions. Unfortunately, compassionately, most of them need a lot of tough-love & therapy. They won’t get that because: Trashademia has

¹⁸ <https://nypost.com/2020/09/24/face-facts-black-lives-matter-is-all-about-hate/>

¹⁹ <https://www.brightworkresearch.com/blms-anti-white-and-anti-male-and-anti-nuclear-family-basis/>

²⁰ <https://www.cnn.com/2022/09/04/us/black-lives-matter-executive-lawsuit/index.html>

²¹ <https://thefederalist.com/2020/09/22/blm-and-1619-project-scrub-radical-beliefs-from-their-websites/>

²² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cAMJSFISg-Y>

²³ <https://legalinsurrection.com/2021/01/flashback-2020-six-months-of-antifa-blm-looting-rioting-and-chaos/>

²⁴ <https://www.breitbart.com/crime/2020/08/02/blm-demands-cut-louisville-businesses-profits-protection/>

²⁵ <https://nypost.com/2020/07/24/washington-post-settles-250m-suit-with-covington-teen-nick-sandmann/>

²⁶ <https://www.foxnews.com/us/verdict-kyle-rittenhouse-not-guilty>

²⁷ <https://www.lifenews.com/2021/09/10/feminist-calls-killing-babies-in-abortions-a-sacred-ritual/>

²⁸ <https://conservativefiringline.com/feminist-kill-male-babies-kill-men-create-female-species/>

²⁹

<https://www.foxnews.com/opinion/illiteracy-is-a-national-emergency-unfolding-across-america-and-its-only-getting-worse>

³⁰ Warning, this is disturbing propaganda: <https://farleftfacts.org/white-people/math-yes-math-is-racist/>

³¹ <https://www.amazon.com/White-Fragility-People-About-Racism-ebook/dp/B07638ZFN1>

³² <https://knowyourmeme.com/memes/the-left-cant-meme>

³³ <https://www.nationalreview.com/2002/06/why-feminists-arent-funny-jonah-goldberg/>

already invented a slew of anti-tough faux diseases to keep them labeled, drugged, removed from their personal power axis³⁴, and incapable of reading and articulating opposing views³⁵.

- ❖ Race-hustlerism has left the small confines of a few NAACP wannabes that fell off the turnip truck while pushing specific Democratic agendas, and turned into major “fact-check” corporate payoffs. They now include all sorts of anti-white hucksters, including white people who brown themselves³⁶ and pretend to be black³⁷, just to get in on ‘Victim Currency.’^{38 39} One of the saddest facts of history in America and abroad, is a consistent drumbeat, generation to generation, of hucksters who blame “whitey” (or Jews, or Asians, or Africans even) for their own life failures, problems, and short-comings. Demanding reparations has become mere middle ground with the race-hustlers. They are literally promoting segregationism⁴⁰ (illegally, and in public schools!), stealing elections⁴¹, and even the idea that people of color (POC) are less human somehow and cannot help but steal. They’ve lobbied to get rid of truth, grades, logic, and math, in a society where it is clearly *only beneficial* to know math, logic, programming, and how to use the Law to your advantage. It reminds the author of this line from Kung Pow: Enter the Fist, “*This is Wimp Lo... we have taught him wrong on purpose, as a joke.*” ... the Stupid Kid replies, “*My-Face-to-Your-Fist Style, how’d you like it?*”

Idiocracy is Big Money

The movie “Idiocracy” was meant as a parody, but it seems almost mimsical how the elite, or the People, have conformed to it so quickly. Of course, there is major \$\$ behind the Agenda. They’ve paid for the Civil War, and they intend to have it! China has projected a glorious victory in WWII⁴², and they will provide Unrestricted Warfare⁴³ until they have it!⁴⁴ The Muslim Brotherhood has come to America to out-breed the West and spread Sharia... and they will invade Congress till they have it! The anarcho-communists have desired a revolution that will be televised, and they will burn perfectly working capitalist, minority-owned businesses and communities till they have it. The race-hustlers will get relevance through racial hatred to defend their proposition that white kids are inherently racist... and they will tear down as many statues as they can to get you to understand they mean business! (Paid for by George Soros⁴⁵).

The point is that simpsters, whether they commit treason, or defend it, vote for a daughter-raping President (who stole the 2020 election and got away with it) and defend his crackhead pedophile son, well,

³⁴ Literally an ability to be centered, balanced, etc. One of these Stupid Kids, “Destiny”, literally cannot sit upright at a debate. The irony is that such people think they are incredibly intelligent, but in fact they are just being overtly pedantic.
³⁵ The author spent time trying to explain this to one - Liberal Cluck - and eventually the social medialite (simp) banned the author, not for offensive words, or ad hominems, but because he lost a debate on climate change, and couldn’t take the collapse of his Safe Space Bubble. He keeps, by contrast, space for a known jew-hating *racist*, because it is easier than asking “why am I so fascist?” He lives in a van, alone, and fails at social studies at a local community college (at age 26), but considers himself a top tier debater. With zero life accomplishments, and no real prospects, the author cannot help feel a little sorry for the Stupid Kid. DEBATE: Liberal Cluck Vs RamonC - Moderated By Drunk Dronetek (Once Cluck starts talking about his having taken “a big shit once”... well ... it was definitely well over by then)

³⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shawn_King

³⁷ <https://news.yahoo.com/shawn-king-biracial-black-lives-matter-controversy-031401699.html>

³⁸ <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/inside-shawn-king-shadowy-6-084611616.html>

³⁹ <https://www.westernjournal.com/shawn-king-ruins-innocent-cops-life-then-claims-hes-the-real-victim/> POS Supreme!

⁴⁰ <https://www.dailywire.com/news/segregation-all-rage-black-lives-matter-groups-amanda-prestigiacom>

⁴¹ Statistical and geotracking data fact. The mules cost a mere \$/mail-in-ballot; see “2000 Mules.”

⁴² “Three Body Problem,” trilogy by Liu Cixing

⁴³ <https://www.c4i.org/unrestricted.pdf>

⁴⁴ <https://archive.org/details/unrestricted-warfare>

⁴⁵ <https://nationalinterest.org/blog/reboot/708-million-how-much-george-soros-spent-politics-one-year-alone-167068>

they're ultimately no different than the lapdogs and slavers that tear at society now, fomenting the Stupid to spread. It oozes into cities, city councils, and communities because the people are spiritually weak, but also because big, big money - partially paid for by [Satanic] Human Flesh Industry - powers it.

The interest in destroying the healthy, capitalistic, Christian, fabric of society sure seems like a Hydra (Nazi) plot⁴⁶... and wouldn't you know the CIA (Deep State) vowed to make Americans believe lies⁴⁷, and imported Nazis and Commies in after WWII. In other words the failure of liberalism is not that ideas and words don't work... it's that it's so open that people's brains fall out and the Agendizers make Agendites out of any of them. New ideas are fine; like clothes you try them on. But if you cannot tell the difference between good and bad ideas, what is there to conserve, what is there to be free for? Without values, and being willing to sell your soul out for anything, pretty soon you're not human anymore: you're a POS.

Equity is not Equality

The idea that you will force equality - create some utopia - is already a well known, documented, and philosophically proven slippery slope into genocide. There's no natural mechanism, and so attempts to use the law and police state, will only result (as any anti-MIMS does) in only one kind of equality that can exist at that point: misery.

The misery of genocide, cultural genocide, eugenicide, deforestation and environmental destruction, and of socially engineered racial hatred are the well known products of fascism and all forms of Marxism. Don't settle for anything short of humanistic egalitarianism. In short: real freedoms, and not fake ones given by the Technocracy, Corporocracy, and fascist dictators like in a "Brandonana Republicstan."⁴⁸

Conclusion

Learn the difference between tolerance and acceptance. Reject anti-science agendizing, Orwellianism, treason, and other POS behaviors. **Be a part of the change you want to see in the world, not just random, haphazard change that has no meaning, origin (that you understand), or pro-humanism.**

Oh and one other thing. When someone tells you the Truth and it stings, that person isn't your enemy, they are your friend. The ones in the echo chamber, selling you sweet-nothings and whispering weakness and fear into you: they are your real enemy. Consider the difference between medicine and sugary sweet snacks. If you cannot understand even this, then congrats, you're on the road to a messy POS path to the dark side.

"There is a way which seems right to a man, but the end thereof are the ways of death."⁴⁹

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

⁴⁶ OPERATION PAPERCLIP: <https://www.theblackvault.com/documentarchive/operation-paperclip/>

⁴⁷ And the Quora when the woman testified this happened, and the Quora about her post both have disappeared. <https://www.quora.com/Did-Barbara-Honegger-comment-on-this-forum-about-former-CIA-Director-William-Casey>

Note: the author noted she did this and found proof: <https://bit.ly/3rfdUS8>

⁴⁸ "Let's Go Brandon!" +Banana Republic+stan

⁴⁹ Proverbs 14:12